

THE LIFE AND WORK OF PEOPLE'S ARTIST OF UZBEKISTAN BATYR ZAKIROV

Abdusattorova Sayyora Akmalovna

Head of the department "Training pedagogues in pop performance" at
the National Pop Art Institute named after Batyr Zakirov under the
State Conservatory of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11525216>

Annotation. This article will talk about the Uzbek singer, a wonderful artist, one of the founders of the dynasty, holder of the title of People's Artist Batyr Zakirov.

Keywords. Singer, pop, song, A.N. Ostrovsky, conservatory, "Uzbekkino", folklore, opera.

Introduction:

Batyr Karimovich Zakirov is an outstanding Uzbek, Soviet singer, artist and literary critic. People's Artist of the Uzbek SSR (1965). He sang songs in different genres: Uzbek folk songs, songs of his own composition, songs of Uzbek and Russian composers, indeed, the pop genre was largely influenced by the work of the Botirov dynasty; it is worth mentioning this: the Zakirov dynasty is a family of Uzbek artists who made a huge contribution to the art of music Uzbekistan of the 20th century. The head of the dynasty is an opera singer, People's Artist of Uzbekistan Karim Zakirov, son Batyr Zakirov is a singer, actor, artist. The People's Artist of Uzbekistan is the founder of the Uzbek professional pop singing (performing) hall.

He also sang foreign hits, mostly in their original form, because he knew several foreign languages. A favorite of the people, he was called the Uzbek nightingale. He is still remembered not only at home, but also abroad. Even today, before our eyes is a young singer embodied in the image. His songs still resonate and the good deeds he did live on.

Famous Uzbek artist, singer, actor and literary figure, People's Artist of Uzbekistan. Batyr Zakirov was born on April 26, 1936. Vocal Faculty of the Tashkent State Conservatory named after A.N. Studied at the directing department of the Tashkent Institute of Theater and Art named after Ostrovsky. In 1956, he created the youth ensemble "Youth" and soon gained fame and recognition. A person who heard the singer's voice would certainly remember her voice and love her songs. He had a pure, touching, and already unique, "nightingale-like" quality, as if soft voice timbre, stunning from the heart. At the international festival of youth and students in Moscow in 1957, he first performed "Arabian tango." This song, recorded on a record, spreads like lightning throughout the world and is still loved by fans of her talent.

By the end of the 50s and 60s, he became very popular in the USSR as a performer of various genres. Nature endowed him with the talent of serving, giving him the brightest facets - a unique voice. He sang with all his being: opera arias, Uzbek folk songs, songs of Soviet composers, foreign hits. His voice was heard on radio and television, his concerts created a great sensation among fans, and in his solo concerts there was no room for extra steps.

The singer's rich repertoire was also impressive. Not only skillfully performed Uzbek songs emerged from this repertoire, but to this day no one can compete with his beautiful and expressive performance. It was in his performance that songs in Italian, French, Spanish, Russian, and Greek were heard on the Uzbek stage in the 60s. Batyr Zakirov is one of the organizers of the State Variety Orchestra of Uzbekistan. The development of Uzbek pop art

began with his creativity, which is characterized by national features, addressing the theme of nationality. 1972 Batyr Zakirov created and directed the first Music Hall in the east in Tashkent, and was also its director, artistic director and soloist. He managed to combine oriental folklore with modern pop trends and arouse interest in it among both musicians and the general public.

The singer was not yet 30 years old; she was awarded the title of Honored Artist of Uzbekistan. B. Zakirov was gifted in many other areas of creativity: fine arts, directing, characterization. Also acted in films. One of the most famous films with the participation of Batyr Zakirov is "Youth of a Genius", filmed in 1982 by director Elor Ishmukhamedov. Together with their favorite singer Bakhtiyor Ikhtierov, Furkat Fayziev, ATO Mukhamajonov, Rano Kubaeva, Vytautas Tomkus, Vasily Chkhaidze, Dzhaniq Fayziev, Shukhrat Ergashev, Murad Radzhabov, Leonard Babakhanov, Konstantin Butaev, Maksud Mansurov, Nabi Rakhimov, Khamza Umarov, Rustam Urazaev, Javlon Khamroev, Dzhuna Davitashvili.

Batyr Zakirov traveled a lot around the Republic. Everyone in the Zakirov family is gifted: Naufal Zakirov, Luiza Zakirova, Farukh Zakirov. Batyr Zakirov died suddenly. From a young age he was seriously ill and seemed to be in a hurry to do everything he wanted in a short period of time. On January 23, 1985, residents of Tashkent said goodbye to the singer. He landed at the Chigatai Nadir cemetery. By decree of the former President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov, Batyr Zakirov was posthumously awarded the Order of Great Merit. He also has the greatest reward - popular love and great memory

Considering the enormous importance of the creative heritage of one of the founders of National Variety Art, a great artist, People's Artist of Uzbekistan Batyr Zakirov, who made an invaluable contribution to the popularization of modern Uzbek culture on a global scale, increasing the spirituality of our people through his creative and social activities, educating the younger generation in the spirit of love and devotion to the Motherland, national and universal values. celebration of the 85th anniversary of his birth and for the purpose of perpetuating memory:

1. The proposal of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Union of Composers and Composers of Uzbekistan, the National Agency "Uzbekkino", the Republican Center for Spirituality and Education, the Academy of Arts, the Agency for Youth Affairs and representatives of the public was approved on the widespread celebration in 2021 of the 85th anniversary of the birth of the national artist of Uzbekistan Batyr Zakirov

2. The composition of the organizing committee for the celebration of the 85th anniversary of the birth of People's Artist of Uzbekistan Batyr Zakirov (hereinafter referred to as the organizing committee) was approved in accordance with the appendix.

3. The organizing committee (A. Aripov) within a month developed and approved a program of events to celebrate the 85th anniversary of the birth of People's Artist of Uzbekistan Batyr Zakirov, providing for the following.

In addition, a national Higher School of Variety named after the People's Artist of Uzbekistan Batyr Zakirov was created in Tashkent, where a memorial complex and museum in memory of the singer were erected. The Academy of Arts announced a competition to create a monument to Batyr Zakirov and install it in the city of Tashkent in the prescribed manner.

A memorial plaque was installed at house No. 3 on Navoi Street in Tashkent, Shaykhantakhur district, where Batyr Zakirov lived.

The street on which the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan is located, where Batyr Zakirov studied, is named after Batyr Zakirov

References:

1. National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan Tashkent 2000-2005
2. Musical dictionary I. Akbarov Tashkent 1987
3. www.lex.uz
4. Hasanov B., Uzbek documentary cinema, t., 1972;

